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EMERGENCE OF PROCESS FACTORS FOR WINNING BUSINESS DEALS AMIDST THE ETERNAL DEBATE ON PERSONAL RELATIONSHIPS VERSUS SUPPLIER CAPABILITY FOR WINNING CLIENT CONTRACTS

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Abstract

There have been continuous discussions on what could be the most important factor that influence organizational buying behaviours. While the ongoing debate of business and personal relationships versus capabilities of vendor and their relative importance is always observed for winning Business deals. We now need to consider how much each of these can also exert influence on Business buying decisions when purchase process or Process orientation is the ruling factor in client purchase decisions. Supply chain functions are evolving and are digitizing along with business processes. Technology is playing a vital role in digitizing every process of businesses. This is enabling transparency in every process with the reduction in manual interventions. Purchase functions are also getting rapidly digitized. Artificial intelligence (AI) is also adding value to the digitizing processes. Large organizations look forward to Vendor programs and run an exhaustive vendor selection and qualification process. They are receptive to digitization process. And businesses and purchase processes are getting digitized with tech tool and AI adoption.

Keywords: IT/Ites, Finance, Personal relationships, contracts

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INTRODUCTION

India's IT / ITES trade body, NASSCOM, has come out with reports that provides some insights the share of digital sales revenues (www.nasscom.in). The major points considered by NASSCOM are:

- Indian IT / ITES revenues have crossed USD 200 billion.
30% revenue of this is from Digital sales and transformations.
Over 15% YOY growth seen in the global and Indian sales.
Even the domestic Indian consumption have shown nearly 10% YOY growth.

Some of these indicators are shown in the following graphics:

FY 2022: Strong Growth -\$227 Bn revenue, \$30 Bn Incremental Revenue in the Year

Fig 01: NASSCOM report on digital and IT economy

According to the report, 30 – 32% of the projects in the above set are from digital transformations and close to 66% of the large deals are for digital transformation projects with 25% YOY growth.

As digitization would be rampant in the industry, process orientation of all business processes would become imminent. It would therefore be imperative for suppliers to understand business processes both theoretically and digitally of their clients for winning business contracts.

As researchers we studied some of the various factors that influences large business purchases. We observe that process also plays crucial role in Business decisions for large purchases.

Objective of study: In this paper we try to understand the effect of Process factors in decision making for B2B purchases. And we also try to understand its influence and effect on the organizational buying behaviour.

Research methodology: We referred to various literatures for the study. We did secondary research on articles from 1960 to 2023 with more emphasis on articles post 2015 to study the evolution of purchase as a function and the processes that evolved with the purchase functions.

We also prepared a questionnaire for B2B respondents to capture their buying process responses. The Process and capability variables were as follows:

Vendor Capability Variables	
Q6_Existingvendor_givebestproposal	Existing vendor gives best service
Q7_PriceWinsdeal	Capable vendor gives best price – New / Existing
Q8_Rightsolutionwindeal	Capable vendor gives best solution – New / Existing
Q11_Contractto_Newvendor	Client is willing to offer contract to new vendor based on his capability.
Purchase Process Variables	
Q3_NDA_with_Vendor	Client signs up NDA with vendor during RFP process.
Q4_Multiple_Vendor_check	Client evaluates multiple vendors before awarding contract.
Q5_Checkfinance_vendor	Client seeks financial data of participating vendors to engage for long term contracts.

Table 01: Vendor capability vs. Purchase Process Variables

Our respondents were predominantly people working in purchase and IT functions of organizations like IT heads, CIO, Purchase and operations managers and directors.

The population considered were any corporations with a purchase panel consisting of influencers and decision makers. The employees size of target respondent companies selected for the survey were 350 employees and above.

As the population size was indeterminate, we looked at sampling by proportion method. After the calculations we arrived at a figure of 384 sample size.

Data collection with the respondents were done by personal interaction, telephone conversations, and circulating questionnaire through online method like Email, Google forms, linked in connections etc. Around 417 data points were collected and after cleaning the data, we could collect 379 records as sample.

LITERATURE REVIEW:

Uluga, et al, 2006, refers to the practice in his paper wherein existing customers engage with the clients at the early stage of RFP so that they can build the requirements as per the capabilities suiting them.

Some authors like Emiliani, 2000, in his paper refers to the concept of Reverse auction which tests the pricing capabilities of the vendors to the core, and which is widely used in today’s purchase process for commodity and standard technology purchases.

Technology provides an important enablement for any business process. Purchase processes are also getting automated, and tech enabled. Martin, et al, 2005, in their paper studies the ERP implementation of a major oil company. The results observed were interesting. They found that the processes had reduced duplication, reduced processes errors, and work was fast tracked. Ecommerce is also foraying into B2B processes. Osmonbekov, et al, 2002, in their work bring out the merits of using ecommerce in B2B purchases. They suggest that ecommerce tools helps in seamless communications and brings out transparency

between buyers and sellers and therefore help in effective business engagement. Sidorova, et al, 2012, in their paper explains the emergence of Enterprise IT teams for technology buying requirements. They define the roles and responsibilities of the actors in the team and their work flows so that the buying processes are defined well. Rodriguez, et al, 2020, in his paper focuses on the importance of digital transformation. The authors Zhou, et al, 2022, in their work try to bring out the concept of digital platforms and their influence on the B2B buying processes. According to them these platforms help in enhancing supplier performance as the platforms are designed to bring transparency and enhance supplier's visibility with the client. They bring out the concept of syndicated buying among closed groups of buyers and suppliers and how such digital platforms help in achieving the same.

Upreti, et al, 2021, in their paper mention the importance of Artificial intelligence and its potential use in mapping buying patterns to sellers for seamless supply chain. According to the authors, the AI tools can map the supplier capabilities to buyers and vice versa. All the requirement fulfilment can be done with prompts provided by AI tools. These tools also help buyers with best buying options and best pricing options too. Some authors like Boyd, et al, 2019, in their work go to the extent of suggesting the adaption of virtual reality in buying process. According to these authors, the Virtual reality helps in effective visualization experience for buyers to make informed buying decisions. These ideas are also echoed by authors like Hollensen, et al, 2022, who suggest the adaption of metaverse to emulate buyer supplier transactions. Chang, 2022, in his work point to reports of Gartner.com and tries to convey that AI will become more powerful in every business process including purchase process going forward. As processes are getting more automated, AI will start controlling the processes and thereby reduce human intervention.

This debate of AI and human capacity is debated widely. Authors Lemarquis, et al, 2022 also tries to debate in their paper the competition between AI and human capacity and according to them the digitization will eventually lead to AI replacing human work on purchase processes. Saha. S, et al, 2023, in their work also suggest that process and capability helps vendors win business contracts. Authors such as Ferenhof, et al, 2022, in their research also come up with ideas as maintaining knowledge management systems that can help in effective AI adaption and implementation.

As digitization and IT transformations are changing the buying processes. Sellers are also adapting new sales methodologies to automate sales processes. Gartner, and Mckinsey in their 2022 reports write about digital sales processes where in every sales processes are aligned to customer centric approach and companies are transforming their sales talent to understand the concepts of buyer's journey and digital transformations so that the sales cycle quickly adapts to the dynamic business environments. These concepts are further supported by authors like Badrinarayan, et al, 2022, who suggest that companies can adapt to technology-based sales transformation that would enhance their capabilities and thereby enhance the relationship with their customers. The following infographic of Mckinsey shows some details on the emergence of digital sales model which is slowly replacing traditional field sales approach.

Hybrid and digital are the fastest-growing sales roles.

Net change in sales roles, percent of respondents, US only¹

¹Q: over the past year, how has the size of your company's sales force in the following areas changed?
Source: McKinsey & Company Global B2B Pulse, Nov 2021, n = 602

McKinsey & Company

Fig 02: Hybrid and Digital are the fastest- growing sales roles

Authors like Cartwright, et al, 2022, in their study come up with ideas like encouraging the use of social platforms like LinkedIn to connect with buyers and sellers. They also suggest the adaption of influential marketing wherein a digital influencer can be employed to market the products and solutions of the seller.

Certain institutional buying like government / public sector buying are heavily process oriented. Event to firm up the requirements they will roll request for information followed by RFP. These institutions are driven by neutrality norms and must maintain high levels of integrity and transparency. In India, with the introduction of Government eMarket-place, all major government departments, institutions and banks have to list their requirements on the portal and the selection of vendor is done in a very meticulous and scientific manner. The selection is highly process oriented and

involves high levels of qualification and documentation. As aforementioned, the digital sales team follow buyer’s journey in the funnel of the sales team. Marvasti, et al, 2021, suggests that there are following stages in the funnel movement of buying cycle as perceived by selling companies to track their funnel movement and buyer’s interest:

Fig 03: Proposed framework for the buying cycle

The above framework can imply that if a buyer comes for casual learning without any actual need then it would be in ‘No Funnel’ stage. If the buyer actually sees a need and comes to the seller seeking information in form of webinar attendance or downloading any details form website or an initial email, then it would be an ‘Early Funnel’ stage. When the seller identifies the need and suggest appropriate solution for the buyer’s needs, it qualifies to ‘Middle Funnel’ stage. When the engagement qualifies for demo, pilot, trials, proposal and pricing discussions the stage would be ‘Late Funnel’.

Gartner has also recommended some of the activities that buyers must follow before they can engage vendors and work complete purchasing. The activities include the following:

- Problem identification. The Buyers should work with user groups to identify the problem / pain areas that will help in identify the business need.
- Solution exploration: after identifying the problem/need, buyers cab work towards understanding what will fulfil their needs / problems.
- Requirements building: buyers will have to understand what requirements needs to be fulfilled to complete the need or solving the problem.
- Supplier selection: buyers need to work towards identifying potential suppliers who could help in fulfilling the requirements.
- Validation: Buying groups must validate the requirements for the proposed solution.

- Consensus creation: Buyers must get the sign off on scope of work from influencers, decision makers, user group and other stake holders.

Fig 04: Activities that buyers should complete

HYPOTHESES:

Based on the details obtained we try to test the following Hypothesis.

- H1: There exists a correlation between vendor capability and client placing order.*
- H2: Evaluation of multiple vendors will disrupt chances of renewing existing business with current vendors.*

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

We conducted secondary research by referring to some important literary references. Request for proposal (RFP) forms one of key process of purchase evaluation. Krishnan, M. S., 2018, in his paper focuses on the importance of defining the RFP and the terms clearly. He has proposed a model that lists the priorities for building RFP, so that the suppliers can work on delivery process clearly.

DATA INTERPRETATION AND ANALYSIS:

It is interesting to note the emerging trends in buying and selling engagements. As mentioned earlier we collected data from online, phone and personal interaction methods. The number of responses collected were 417 of which a sample size of 380 was considered post cleaning up of data. After the data was ready for processing. We conducted the following analysis on them:

- **Skewness test:** The results obtained from skewness test exhibited normality
- **Mahalanobis distance test:** This test helped us to understand that there were no outliers in the data used.
- **ANOVA test:** this test helped us to understand that the data is heterogeneous in nature.

- **Correlation analysis:** the correlation tests and their results found that no two variables have significant correlation of 0.9 and above.

The above data processing tests confirm that the data was normal, heterogeneous, and mostly mutually exclusive variables in the absence of significant correlations.

HYPOTHESIS TESTING

After processing and analysing the data we work towards testing the hypotheses.

H1 (*There exists a relationship between vendor capability and client placing order.*) for this hypothesis from the correlation matrix derived from the data analysis, we check the Sig Value (P Value) of Variables Q8_Rightsolutionwindeal, Q10_Renewwithexistingvendor and Q11_Contractto_Newvendor. This implies that if the client is satisfied with right solution, he would also be willing to roll the contract to existing / new vendor.

We go by the logic that if the solution is right and completely acceptable to the client, he is likely to award contract irrespective of existing or new vendor. With this thought, if we compare the sig

values of variables Q8_Rightsolutionwindeal, Q10_Renewwithexistingvendor and Q11_Contractto_Newvendor we find the following observation

Sig Value for Q8_Rightsolutionwindeal and Q10_Renewwithexistingvendor = 0.318 (31.8%)

Sig Value for Q8_Rightsolutionwindeal and Q11_Contractto_Newvendor = 0.156 (15.6%)

Sig Value is greater than 0.05. Therefore we can accept the null Hypothesis.

H4 (There exists a correlation between Evaluation of multiple vendors and the renewal of business with existing vendors.): for this hypothesis from the correlation matrix derived from the data analysis, we check the Sig Value (P Value) of Variables Q4_Multiple_Vendor_check and Q10_Renewwithexistingvendor. This implies that if the client is evaluating multiple vendors, then there is a chance that existing vendor’s chances of winning the deal is disrupted or less.

The sig value of Variables Q4_Multiple_Vendor_check and Q10_Renewwithexistingvendor is 0.000 (significantly lower)

Sig Value is less than 0.05. Therefore we may not be able to reject this null Hypothesis.

HYPOTHESIS TESTING RESULTS

Hypothesis	Statement	Sig Level	Decision Clause	Decision
H1	<i>There exists a relationship between vendor capability and client placing order.</i>	0.157 0.318	> 0.05	Null Hypothesis Accepted
H2	<i>Evaluation of multiple vendors will disrupt chances of renewing existing business with current vendors.</i>	0	< 0.05	Null Hypothesis Rejected

Table 02: Hypotheses Testing Results

When we analyse the responses of the questions for process variables, we find that almost all the respondents follow the process meticulously. This can be seen the their responses to the following questions.

Fig 05: NDA Signed with Vendors

As we observe, 91% of respondents have answered that they sign up NDA with vendors.

Fig 06: Evaluating multiple vendors

99% of the respondents agree that they evaluate multiple suppliers before deciding on closing the purchase with any vendor.

Fig 07: Checking for finance of vendors

Around 94% of respondents agree that it is a good practice to health of vendors before engaging them in purchase process.

The above process parameters indicate that the Clients find process and adherence of process very critical for any kind of organizational strategic purchase decisions.

Not satisfied with the above observations we further investigated the data for more tests.

Observations:

We performed cluster analysis by data reduction techniques to further understand the nature of relationships between the variables. We used the variable analysis and data reduction techniques in SPSS as follows.

We get the following outputs for our study:

Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings			Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	2.467	18.974	18.974	2.467	18.974	18.974	1.660	12.769	12.769
2	1.612	12.404	31.378	1.612	12.404	31.378	1.599	12.300	25.069
3	1.467	11.282	42.660	1.467	11.282	42.660	1.566	12.047	37.115
4	1.210	9.304	51.964	1.210	9.304	51.964	1.532	11.787	48.903
5	1.126	8.658	60.622	1.126	8.658	60.622	1.500	11.541	60.444
6	1.106	8.507	69.129	1.106	8.507	69.129	1.129	8.685	69.129
7	.921	7.083	76.212						
8	.729	5.604	81.817						
9	.650	4.997	86.814						
10	.582	4.474	91.288						
11	.437	3.358	94.646						
12	.403	3.100	97.745						
13	.293	2.255	100.000						

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Table 03: Total Variance Table.

Scree plots are used to plot Eigen values against the components in the study. The Scree plots help to determine the factors in the Exploratory factor

analysis or components in Principal component analysis. The Scree Plot for the above data is as follows.

Fig 08: Scree Plot

Based on the above data we interpret that there are six components identified by the SPSS tests. This indicate that there are some variables that would group together to denote some meaning.

To further study the phenomenon we use study the component table and the rotated component table.

Component Matrix^a

	Component					
	1	2	3	4	5	6
Q5_Checkfinance_vendor	-.646			.536		
Q1_Vendor_help_in_requirementdiscovery	.635			.458		
Q4_Multiple_Vendor_check	-.630					
Q10_Renewwithexistingvendor	.617	.454				.339
Q2_Knowledgeshare_vendor	.505			.423		
Q9_Satisfiedwith_existingvendorsupport		.602	-.453			
Q8_Rightsolutionwindeal		.519				
Q12_Strongvendorrelationship	.333	.502			.342	
Q3_NDA_with_Vendor			.641	.367		
Q11_Contractto_Newvendor		-.369	.586			
Q6_Existingvendor_givebestproposal		.437	.542			.408
Q13_AM_Jobswitch					.854	.354
Q7_PriceWinsdeal	-.416			-.420		-.574

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.
a. 6 components extracted.

Table 4: Component matrix

importance to the right solution and price for awarding contracts.

Rotated Component Matrix^a

	Component		
	1	2	3
Q7_PriceWinsdeal	.754		
Q4_Multiple_Vendor_check	.700		
Q8_Rightsolutionwindeal	.549		
Q6_Existingvendor_givebestproposal		.829	
Q10_Renewwithexistingvendor	-.364	.787	
Q9_Satisfiedwith_existingvendorsupport			.803
Q11_Contractto_Newvendor			-.772

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.
Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization. ^a
a. Rotation converged in 6 iterations.

Table 5: Rotated component table

The above Rotated component table gives interesting observations. We find three groups of variables grouping with each other. Most important and interesting group to study includes the following variables:

- Q7_PriceWinsdeal: The proposal with best price is awarded the contract
- Q4_Multiple_Vendor_check: The buyers call for multiple vendors to participate in the bid process.
- Q8_Rightsolutionwindeal: The proposal that gives the best solution wins the deal.

The above variables group together. This implies that the variables are following the group of process variables. If the buyers sets a process where he calls multiple vendors to participate then in such scenario as per the bidding process the best price and the right solution becomes decisive factors for any vendor to win the bid. The variance analysis also points this to us. This was also observed by us during the responses received that the clients paid

Implication:

This observation brings out an interesting implication. When purchase process is strict and multiple vendors are included in the bidding process, there will be intense competition between the qualified bidders to show competence in terms of solution and pricing. Therefore, it is interesting to note that these three variables align together. Also, one more interesting factor to be noticed here is that when purchase process is KPI driven, these three variables form a key part of the buyer’s Key performance, and hence the responses of the buyers resonate with their KPI and we see that the three variables align together.

We find another interesting observation is the grouping of variables:

- Q6_Existingvendor_givebestproposal: Existing vendor can give the best proposal during the bid process.
- Q10_Renewwithexistingvendor: the client is likely to renew the contract with the existing vendor at the end of bidding process.

This implies that during the bid process if the existing vendor can provide the best proposal the client could be willing to renew with the same vendor.

Implication: This observation is also interesting to note. Existing vendors, who maintain relationships with the Key clients, will be having multiple touch points in the account and are able to collate information regarding bids from various sources. With this, they can provide the best technological proposal. This helps them renew their

existing business with the key clients. In these cases, relationship plays an important role in maintaining healthy vendor – client relationship so that the vendor has right information to roll out the best proposal and also maintain purchase preference with the key client.

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